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Научная статья

ПОДГОТОВКА К ИТОГОВОМУ КОНТРОЛЮ ПО ПРЕДМЕТУ «АНГЛИЙСКИЙ ЯЗЫК» С ПРИМЕНЕНИЕМ ИНТЕРНЕТ-РЕСУРСОВ И ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ

PREPARATION FOR THE FINAL ASSESSMENT IN THE SUBJECT «ENGLISH LANGUAGE» USING INTERNET RESOURCES AND TECHNOLOGIES

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В данной статье рассматриваются возможности использования, целесообразность, функции и требования к применению интернет-ресурсов и интернет-технологий в процессе подготовки к итоговому контролю по иностранному языку. Определены функции, которые выполняют интернет-ресурсы. Приведены основные требования, которые необходимо учитывать при отборе необходимого интернет-ресурса для подготовки к итоговой аттестации по иностранному языку. Представлены рекомендации для преподавателей по выбору готовых интернет-ресурсов и созданию своих собственных.

This article discusses the possibilities of using, expediency, functions and requirements for the use of Internet resources and Internet technologies in the process of preparing for the final control in a foreign language. The functions performed by Internet resources are defined. The main requirements that must be taken into account when selecting the necessary Internet resource for preparation for final certification in a foreign language are given. Recommendations for teachers on choosing ready-made Internet resources and creating their own are presented.

Ключевые слова: итоговый контроль, интернет-ресурсы, интернет-технологии, учебный процесс, информационно-образовательная среда, результаты обучения.

Key words: final assessment, Internet resources, Internet technologies, educational process, information and educational environment, learning outcomes.

The Russian school education system is currently going through a very difficult period. Requirements for the quality of education are constantly increasing. The implementation of the updated Federal State Educational Standards for General Education aims to achieve sufficiently high results, the formation of which is verified using various types, forms and means of control.

Federal State Educational Standards contain, along with requirements for the results of mastering educational programs, requirements for the conditions for their implementation. It is no longer possible to imagine teaching schoolchildren without a modern information and educational environment, the basis of which is the Internet [6]. In accordance with the Federal State Educational Standard, the information and educational environment of an educational organization is obliged to provide students with access to EOR, as well as means of determining the level of knowledge and assessing competencies [5, p. 31]. Electronic (digital) educational resources can be posted on federal educational platforms, can be developed and posted by subject teachers themselves directly in the information and educational environment of the school. They represent a set of objects for a more effective organization of the educational process [4].

Other resources, including Internet resources, can also be used. But taking into account the requirements of the Federal State Educational Standard, they must be verified [5, p. 35]. In other words, they must be reliable and verified. Researchers note the variety of functions performed by educational Internet resources: a source of information, a way to organize the educational process, a way to stimulate educational motivation, and also a means of control [5].

The purpose of this article is to analyze the possibilities and feasibility of using Internet resources and Internet technologies to prepare schoolchildren for the final assessment in a foreign (English) language. In addition, the functions of Internet resources and the requirements for their selection and use are considered. Let us clarify that Internet resources are electronic (digital) teaching aids, for the creation and application of which modern computer and information and communication technologies are used, and the Internet is the place of placement. Internet resources used in teaching English are very diverse and can be used both to solve specific educational problems (for example, the formation of vocabulary skills) and to organize the educational process in a foreign language [2]. For example, this can be a separate educational task with detailed instructions for its implementation or a sequence of tasks, where in addition to the instructions, a function for calling up reference material or leading questions, a self-checking function, etc. can be provided. This is very convenient for organizing independent work of students [1]. Analyzing the possibilities of using Internet resources and Internet technologies to prepare for the final assessment in a foreign language (Compulsory State Examination – CSE and Unified State Examination – USE), we consider all the resources that are suitable for solving a set of tasks facing a teacher and his students not only immediately before the final assessment, but also over a fairly long period preceding it. With the help of Internet resources, both language skills (phonetic, lexical, grammatical, spelling) and communication skills (to a greater extent listening and meaningful reading skills, although there are also opportunities to develop speaking and writing skills) are successfully developed, and socio-cultural knowledge and skills are formed. In other words, in preparation for the final assessment, there is a place for all the above-mentioned resources and special resources focused on the format of the CSE and USE.

Many digital resources for learning a foreign language are posted on Internet platforms. Among them, it is worth highlighting such well-known video hosting sites as RuTube, YouTube, TED Talks, etc. Such sites as Englishpage.com, Duolingo, WordWall are successfully used to form and develop lexical and grammatical skills. Online boards such as Miro have great functionality. Here, it is possible to post a wide variety of resources, design schemes, create mind maps, with the help of which students, for example, can systematize lexical material on different topics. Internet resources on the "FIPI" (Federal Institute for Pedagogical Measurements) website, the distance learning system «Sdam GIA» («Will Pass State Final Examination») are indispensable for preparing for the state final certification.

The introduction of neural networks is innovative [3]. Thus, Chat GPT (openai.com) is capable of generating texts on any topic, for any level of foreign language proficiency. With the help of artificial intelligence, you can create exercises for any text (including those previously written by Chat GPT itself). The Deep English resource is actively developing the practice of communicating with a neural network assistant not only in written but also in oral format. Thanks to the introduction of new technologies, students can receive timely feedback and draw appropriate conclusions based on the information provided by artificial intelligence (for example, about mistakes made).

Modern Internet technologies allow you to use various forms of interaction between students in preparation for the CSE and the USE. For example, a teacher can organize collective work of a study group on their website to develop, for example, the skills of completing written assignments with a detailed answer (e-mail, essay). Network Internet technologies have proven their effectiveness in teaching a foreign language [7]. They allow all participants in the educational process to interact in different modes.

Based on tables with criteria and descriptors, as well as additional assessment tables, students can directly on the website evaluate the work offered on the website by the teacher. If students have a good understanding of the criteria by which their work will be checked by the USE experts, they will be more attentive to all elements of the assignment. By checking the work of their classmates according to the established criteria and evaluating it, students focus on individual elements. If they clearly identify the mistakes made in other students' work, they are more likely to avoid making similar mistakes in their own.

Internet resources used in preparing students for the final assessment in a foreign language perform a number of functions, among which the main ones are the following:

- providing a variety of training exercises to develop language skills and communication skills;
- providing exercises in the format of the CSE and USE, including interactive ones (with the possibility of self-monitoring);
- familiarization with information about the structure of the State Final Assessment in a foreign language, as well as recommendations (instructions) for completing various assignments.

When choosing an Internet resource to prepare for the final assessment in a foreign language, the teacher must be sure that the resource is verified (reliable, tested). The advantage of the resource is the presentation of educational information or control materials in different formats (texts, audio and video recordings, multimedia resources). It is necessary to be able to use resources of varying degrees of complexity in order to ensure a differentiated approach.

Another requirement is that all educational and training materials must be up-to-date. The State Final Examination materials are constantly adjusted and even updated periodically. A foreign language teacher must constantly monitor this process.

Accessibility can also be considered an important requirement. Resources must be easily accessible to all students, regardless of their social, economic or physical status). Ideally, they should be compatible with various technical devices, have an offline mode (without the need for a constant connection to the Internet) and be adapted for children with disabilities).

Interactivity (the ability of students to actively participate in the learning process through interaction with resources) is achieved through Internet technologies, which are constantly being improved.

When making decisions about the use of Internet resources and technologies to prepare for the final assessment in a foreign language, you should always remember about preserving the health of students and comply with the requirements of the SanPiN (Sanitary Rules and Norms).

Thus, it can be stated that Internet resources and Internet technologies perform important functions in preparing for the final assessment in a foreign language. A modern teacher must be well versed in the variety of resources available on the network and be able to create their own. When choosing ready-made Internet resources and creating their own, the teacher must demonstrate a high degree of responsibility. All resources must be reliable, verified. Their use must be appropriate. An excess of resources can only harm students. You should always remember about preserving their health.

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